

Electrochemical detection of fluoride in water using polymer encapsulated Zr-EDTA-PCV reagent

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Manuscript received 28 July 2016, revised 17 October 2016, accepted 20 October 2016

Abstract : Long term exposure to fluoride leads to development of fluorosis in dental, skeletal and non-skeletal forms. Thus its detection by sensitive and reliable method is an urgent need. In this paper, an electrochemical sensor was reported for potentiometric detection of fluoride. The methodology included preparation of a colored paste by mixing stipulated quantity of pyrocatechol violet (PCV), zirconium oxychloride ($ZrOCl_2$) and ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid (EDTA) followed by its *in situ* entrapment in a polymeric membrane made of poly vinyl alcohol (PVA) and gelatin crosslinked with glutaraldehyde on the surface of a working electrode. When the polymer modified electrode was dipped in fluoride contaminated water, a distinct change in potential was observed with concentration of fluoride. The electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was also used to detect fluoride. Both potentiometry and EIS methods were found fruitful in addressing the problem of measurement of fluoride contaminated drinking water. The LOD of the sensor was found to be 0.325 ppm and sensitivity 7 mV/ppb.

Keywords : Fluoride, fluorosis, polymer-electrode, sensor, potentiometry, EIS.

Introduction

Fluoride is an inorganic anion of fluorine with the chemical formula F^- and is a naturally occurring element in minerals, geochemical deposits and natural water systems. This enters food chains through consumption of water. The main source of fluoride in ground water is fluoride-bearing rocks such as fluor spar, fluorite, cryolite, fluorapatite and hydroxylapatite¹. There are several uses of fluoride and other fluorine compounds in industries such as fertilizers, production of high purity graphite, semiconductors, electrolysis of alumina, rocket fuels, polymer and plastics production, teflon and tefzel production, toothpaste, purify public water supplies, uranium production, air conditioning etc.²⁻⁵. Though fluoride enters the body through water, food, industrial exposure, drugs, cosmetics, etc., drinking water is the major source (75%) of daily intake of fluoride. Long term ingestion of drinking water having high levels of fluoride concentration cause serious health problems to human being. According to WHO guideline, the threshold limit of fluoride concentration in drinking water is 1.5 mg/L⁵. Excess fluoride beyond that limit leads to dental and skeletal fluorosis as well as non skeletal manifestations⁶.

Fluorosis is an incurable but preventable disease marked by nausea, flu, stomach upset, respiratory problems, arthritic pain and cancer⁵. Groundwater in India is severely contaminated with fluoride in states like Orissa, Gujarat, Rajasthan and Andhra Pradesh. Orissa has 93 fluoride contaminated sites and almost all districts of Rajasthan, Gujarat and Andhra Pradesh are affected. West Bengal has endemic fluoride contamination predominantly in some areas of Purulia^{7,8}, Bankura⁹, Birbhum, Malda, South Dinajpur district. Thus a handy and low cost detection method for estimation of fluoride in drinking water is essential and relevant in the present scenario. The techniques based on ion selective electrode¹⁰ and colorimetry^{11,12} are the most satisfactory for fluoride detection but these suffer from certain limitations. SPADNS method is widely used as a standard method of fluoride detection¹³ but this method needs sample pre-treatment like distillation as some common ions like Al^{3+} , PO_4^{3-} , Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} etc. interfere in the measurement. Apart from these standard methods various chromogenic dyes are used as reagents for chromogenic and fluorogenic chemosensors¹⁴ for sensing fluoride. Among them, pyrocatechol violet (PCV) has been widely used as chelometric reagent¹⁵

which forms blue to blue-violet complexes with metal ions. Balaji *et al.*¹⁶ have studied the naked eye detection of fluoride using aqueous solution of PCV forming ternary complex with Zr^{IV}-EDTA and observed a distinct color change from blue to yellow upon addition of fluoride. This color change is due to the replacement of PCV with fluoride in the complex by ligand exchange mechanism producing the yellow color of uncomplexed PCV. This test with Zr-EDTA-PCV reagent was also performed as selective test for fluoride for screening of some oral fluoroquinolones available in the Indian market¹⁷. The electrochemical sensing of any analyte offers some advantages over these colorimetric methods due to its fast response time, sensitivity, reusability, portability¹⁸. Thus the main objective in this work was to develop low cost electrochemical sensor for fluoride detection below the threshold limit prescribed by WHO. In achieving this goal two methods were tried : (i) potentiometric method and (ii) electrochemical impedance spectroscopy. In both cases the working electrode was modified with *in situ* immobilization of Zr-EDTA-PCV reagent in PVA gelatin crosslinked polymer network. Moreover some measurements of fluoride concentration in unknown samples of groundwater were also done via potentiometry.

Results and discussion

SEM analysis :

Fig. 1 shows the micrograph of porous structure of PVA and gelatin blend copolymerised with glutaraldehyde with and without the coloring agent (Zr-EDTA-PCV). The addition of glutaraldehyde to a solution containing PVA and gelatin gave a crosslinked copolymer due to reaction between NH₂ group of gelatin and CHO of glut-

Fig. 1. SEM image of PVA, gelatin copolymerized matrix crosslinked with glutaraldehyde without Zr-EDTA-PCV (A) and with Zr-EDTA-PCV (B).

araldehyde as well as OH group of PVA. Fig. 1 showed that the pore size of copolymer decreased on addition of the coloring agent due to entrapment of Zr-EDTA-PCV into polymeric porous network.

FTIR analysis :

In Fig. 2, peaks appeared near 3290 cm⁻¹ in all the films containing pure PVA¹⁹ indicating stretching of inter- or intra-molecular hydrogen bonds of O-H²⁰. Addition of Zr-EDTA-PCV in the crosslinked PVA-gelatin-glutaraldehyde matrix resulted in a change in FTIR spectra at around 1560–1640 cm⁻¹. If we compare the % transmittance ratio of 1640 cm⁻¹ and 1560 cm⁻¹ between A and B (Fig. 2), the ratio increased from 0.95 to 1.01 due to addition of Zr-EDTA-PCV. The spectral pattern of B and C in the above said frequency range remained the same. The difference in spectral nature observed for A and B was due to entrapment of Zr-EDTA-PCV in the matrix which eventually affected the amide I moiety^{19,20} of crosslinked copolymer.

In presence of small amount of fluoride, no significant changes could be observed in the FTIR spectra. The addition of F⁻ formed fluoride complexes with Zr-O groups and induced spectral changes in the H-bonded or complex forming moiety of this system. But as the investigating system was very complex, the absorption of different functional groups actually masked the small change. This clearly demonstrated the limitation of spectroscopic method to determine ppm/ppb level of F⁻ in the sample.

Electrochemical measurement :

Potentiometry :

Fig. 3 represented the potentiometric response of PE for different F⁻ concentration in ppm level. The increase in potential with the increase in F⁻ concentration indicated the presence of free PCV. Actually the increase in the concentration of F⁻ increased Zr-F complex formation replacing PCV from Zr-EDTA-PCV and hence showed incremental changes in potential. It could be seen from Fig. 3, that there was a linear relationship between the voltage and fluoride concentration in the concentration range of 0.5–1.5 ppm. The LOD²¹ of the sensor was found to be 0.325 ppm and sensitivity 7 mV/ppb. Thus the modified electrode was sensitive below the WHO guideline limit of F⁻ toxicity.

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra of (A) PVA and gelatin crosslinked with glutaraldehyde, (B) crosslinked copolymer containing Zr-EDTA-PCV and (C) crosslinked copolymer in presence of F^- .

Fig. 4 represented the potentiometric response of PE for different unknown samples including tap water and the corresponding concentrations could be calculated from the calibration plot (Fig. 3). The performance of the sensor was compared with other published results and tabulated (Table 3).

Characterization by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) :

The Nyquist plot (Fig. 5a) was obtained from EIS frequency scanning of bare and immobilized GC electrodes in solution containing 5 mM $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ along with 0.1 M KCl. The Warburg impedance reflect the influence of the mass transport of the electroactive species on the total impedance of the electrochemical cell and in the present modification, this was significant in immobilized PE but when the electrode was dipped in F^- solution of

increasing concentrations, the charge transfer became dominant and we have obtained Randle's equivalent circuit as [R(QR)] same as bare GC (Fig. 5b). Moreover a low frequency straight line was found with a very small semi-circle for bare electrode and a semi-circle at high frequency region in case of modified GC electrode (Fig. 5c) which implied that electron transfer reaction was blocked due to immobilization of electrode surface. Again with increase in F^- concentration there was increase in R_p values (shown in Table 1). This was due to the fact that when more F^- ions were reacting with the Zr-EDTA-PCV, more amount of Zr-F complexes were produced blocking the polymer matrix immobilized on GC electrode surface and therefore the resistance of PE also increased (Fig. 6). The results have been compared by three methods in case of water samples i.e. groundwater obtained locally (Table 2).

Fig. 3. Potentiometric response in V plotted against fluoride concentration in ppm.

Table 1. The fitted parameters obtained by NOVA 1.9.16 software

Concentration of F (ppb)	R_s^a (Ohm)	R_p^a (KOhm)	CPE ^a (μ Mho)
500	203	30.8	24.3
800	207	74.6	22.7
1000	214	85.9	22.6
1500	209	87	24.5
2000	195	84.9	28.2

^a R_s , R_p and CPE were found from equivalent circuit fitted by NOVA 1.9.16.

Table 2. The comparison of results of unknown groundwater samples obtained by different methods

Sample No.	Types of sample	Concentration of F ⁻ of unknown samples of groundwater in ppm		
		Potentiometry ^a	EIS ^a	Standard test kit ^a
1	Tap water	0.50	0.50	Not traceable
2	Unknown 1	0.60±0.05	0.80±0.08	0.50±0.05
3	Unknown 2	4.44±0.04	4.50±0.04	4.00±0.04
4	Unknown 3	3.38±0.03	4.20±0.04	4.00±0.04
5	Sample 4	2.94±0.03	3.10±0.03	3.00±0.03
6	Sample 5	3.80±0.03	3.90±0.03	4.00±0.04
7	Sample 1	2.00±0.02	2.30±0.02	2.50±0.02

^aThe higher concentrations were measured after proper dilution by all three methods.

Experimental

Materials and reagents :

Pyrocatechol violet was purchased from Sigma, $ZrOCl_2 \cdot 8H_2O$ was supplied by HIMEDIA and EDTA was supplied by Qualigenes. Polyvinyl alcohol, gelatin, glut-

Fig. 4. Potentiometric response in V vs unknown water samples.

araldehyde (25%), NaF and all other chemicals were of analytical grade and supplied by E. Merck India.

Instrumentation :

All the test procedures were performed by Autolab Electrochemical Analyzer (PGSTAT 30) using General Purpose Electrochemical System (GPES) software (Ecochemie, Utrecht, The Netherlands). The two terminals of working and reference electrodes were connected to the analyser which was interfaced with a computer. The EIS was recorded from an additional module attached to the PGSTAT 30.

Methodology :

First of all a stock coloring agent was prepared using Zr, EDTA and PCV as follows :

Solution A : The acetate buffer of pH 4.2 was prepared by dissolving 3.7 mL glacial acetic acid and 2.177 g sodium acetate trihydrate in 50 mL water.

Solution B : 0.02 g $ZrOCl_2$, 0.03 g EDTA and 0.001 g pyrocatechol violet were dissolved in water and 25 mL solution A was added to this to make the final volume to 100 mL. This blue colored stock reagent remained stable for nearly 2 weeks at room temperature ($\sim 30^\circ C$).

The working electrode was polished with active alumina (0.05 micron) and washed three times with Milli-Q ($18.2 M\Omega$) water. The electrode surface was then cleaned with ethanol in a sonicator bath for 10 min. 10% PVA solution was prepared using 10 g of PVA in 100 mL water and heating at $70^\circ C$ under continuous stirring for 4–5 h. To 1 mL of this solution, 0.025 g gelatin and 50 μ L stock color reagent were added and mixed well.

Table 3. Comparison of performance of proposed sensor

Sr. No.	Type of sensor	Measurement range (mg/L)	Sample	LOD (mg/L)	Detector element	Stability	Ref.
1.	Colorimetric chemosensor	0.285–2.85	Industrial effluents	8.6	Zr(H ₂ O) EDTA and PV	Stable	16
2.	Colorimetric method	Up to 1.9	Rainwater	0.002	Cyanine dye and TBS	Stable	11
3.	Spectrophotometric method	0–1.0	Groundwater	0.07	Aluminium-resorcin blue complex	Stable	12
4.	Spectrophotometric methods	0–1.40	Water	–	Zirconium SPADNS		13
5.	Potentiometry and EIS	0–2.0	Drinking water	0.325	Zr(H ₂ O) EDTA and PV entrapped in a polymeric membrane	Stable	Present work

Fig. 5. EIS studies of modified electrode (a) Nyquist plot of GC electrode at different concentration of fluoride within the frequency range 0.1 to 10⁵ Hz, (b) and (c) equivalent circuit model for bare and immobilized GC electrode respectively.

20 μL of the mixture was dispersed on the working electrode (glassy carbon) surface and 10 μL of 10% glutaraldehyde added as crosslinker and left for drying at room temperature. This modified electrode was referred to polymer electrode (PE) in the text.

Characterization of PE :

To analyze morphology and spectral results, characterization of synthesized polymer matrix was carried out by SEM and FTIR. The surface morphology of the polymer matrix was characterized by scanning electron microscopy (FEI quanta 200, USA) at an acceleration voltage of 20 kV and different magnification. The FTIR spectra of samples were performed in a Thermo Scientific FTIR instrument (Model Nicolet iS10,) using ATR sampling technique. The spectra over the range 4000–400 cm⁻¹ were obtained at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹.

Preparation of fluoride solution :

100 ppm stock solution of fluoride was prepared. The required strength (0.05–5 ppm) was prepared from this stock by dilution.

Electrochemical measurements :

Potentiometric study :

A glassy carbon working electrode and Ag/AgCl ref-

Fig. 6. Plot of *R_p* value against concentration of fluoride in ppb.

reference electrode were used in 0.1 M acetate electrolyte buffer (pH 4.8) for the electrochemical measurement. A 4 mL volume of buffer electrolyte was used to the two-electrode assembly and stable potentiometric response was equilibrated using a galvanostat/potentiostat (PGSTAT 30). The PE was then dipped in different fluoride solutions of 10 mL volume for 10 min and potentiometric response was measured immediately under zero current condition and using the same buffer electrolyte. A calibration curve was plotted with the potential response after 450 s for each of the F⁻ concentrations and subtracting the response of buffer. The PE was also tested for different groundwater samples collected from local area and the responses were taken by the same method.

EIS study :

The AC impedance analysis was performed with AUTOLAB, PGSTAT 12 (Eco Chemie, The Netherlands) with a frequency response analyzer (version 4.9). The impedance measurement was accomplished by galvanostatic frequency scan. The scanning frequency was set from 0.1 to 10⁵ Hz with modulation amplitude 0.01 mA. The real and imaginary parts of the impedance were calculated using frequency response analyzer (FRA 4.9.006) system software supported with potentiostat/galvanostat PGSTAT 12 (AUTOLAB, Ecochemie B.V., Netherlands). A solution of 5 mM K₃Fe(CN)₆ along with 0.1 M KCl was used as the electrolyte in a two-electrode cell and all measurements were performed at room temperature (22–24 °C). The obtained plots of complex against real components of impedance ($-Z''$ vs Z') were fitted to equivalent circuit model. The best fit analysis was obtained by NOVA 1.9.16 (AUTOLAB; FRA compatible software). The equivalent circuit was fitted as [R(QR)] (Fig. 5b) for bare and [R(QR)W] (Fig. 5c) for immobilized electrode where R referred to the resistance of two kinds, solution resistance R_s and sum of coating resistance and charge transfer resistance as R_p , CPE is the constant phase element (Q) and W is the Warburg impedance (Z_w).

Conclusions

An electrochemical sensing system has been developed for estimation of fluoride in groundwater below the

WHO guideline limit of F⁻ toxicity. The coloring agent composed of Zr-EDTA-PCV was incorporated into a copolymer matrix directly on the working electrode surface and measured the change in potential under zero current condition. The electrochemical measurement showed the sensitivity of the system to be 7 mV/ppb of F⁻ concentration. The EIS results correlated the increase in resistance with increase in fluoride concentration. Since the coloring reagent contained no biological compound, the stability of the polymer encapsulated matrix was found to be high (several months). The sensing system could be used on-site with hand held analyzer.

Acknowledgement

This work has been funded by Department of Science and Technology (DST). Author K. Dutta is woman scientist under DST WOS-A. File No. SR/WOS-A/ET-38/2010 (G).

References

1. G. Manimaran, S. Nellaiappan and A. V. Udayanapillai, *Online International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 2013, **3**, 145.
2. G. Pizzo, M. R. Piscopo, I. Pizzo and G. Giuliana, *Clin Oral Investig.*, 2007, **11**, 189.
3. J. S. Humphrey and R. Amin-Sanayei, in "Vinylidene Fluoride Polymers", *Encyclopedia of Polymer Science and Technology*, 4th ed., Wiley, New York, 2001.
4. G. Siegemund, W. Schwertfeger, A. Feiring, B. Smart, F. Behr, H. Vogel and B. McKusick, "Fluorine Compounds, Organic", *Ullmann's Encyclopedia of Industrial Chemistry*, Wiley VCH, 2000.
5. WHO, Chemical fact sheets : fluoride. in : Guidelines for drinking water quality : incorporation first addendum. Recommendations, Vol. 1, 3rd ed., Geneva, 2006.
6. J. A Alvarez, P. C Karla Mayra. Rezende, Susana María Salazar Marocho, Fabiana B. T. Alves, Paula Celiberti and Ana Lidia Ciamponi, *Med. Oral Patol Oral Cir. Bucal.*, 2009, **14**, 103.
7. H. N. Bhattacharya and S. Chakrabarty, *Curr. Sci.*, 2011, **101**, 152.
8. A. C. Samal, P. Bhattacharya, A. Mallick, M. Ali, J. Pyne and S. C. Santra, *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.*, 2015, **22**, 6220.
9. S. Bhowmick, B. Nath, D. Halder, A. Biswas, S. Majumder, P. Mondal S. Chakraborty, J. Nriagu, P. Bhattacharya, M. Iglesias, G. Roman-Ross, D. Guha Mazumder, J. Bundschuh and D. Chatterjee, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2013, **262**, 915.
10. (a) "Ion-Selective Electrode Determination of Fluoride Ion", California State University Chemistry, 321L Manual, Northridge, CA; (b) "Determination of Fluoride

Dutta *et al.* : Electrochemical detection of fluoride in water using polymer encapsulated Zr-EDTA-PCV reagent

- ride Ion Using an Ion Selective Electrode", CHEM 222 Lab Manual, Truman State University.
11. C. Q. Zhua, J. L. Chenb, H. Zheng, Y. Q. Wu and J. G. Xu, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2005, **539**, 311.
 12. Z. Barghouthi and S. Amereih, *Am. J. Anal. Chem.*, 2012, **3**, 651.
 13. E. Bellack and P. J. Schouboe, *Anal. Chem.*, 1958, **30**, 2032.
 14. C. Suksai and T. Tuntulani, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2003, **32**, 192.
 15. F. J. Green, "Sigma-Aldrich Handbook of Stains, Dyes and Indicators", 2nd ed., Aldrich Chemical Company, University of Minnesota, 1990.
 16. T. Balaji and H. Matsunaga, *Anal. Sci.*, 2005, **21**, 973.
 17. B. K. Singh, D. V. Parwate and S. K. Shukla, *E-J. Chem.*, 2009, **6**, 377.
 18. F. Faridbod, V. K. Gupta and H. A. Zamani, *Int. J. Electrochem.*, 2011, **2011**, 2.
 19. P. M. A. Alves, R. A. Carvalho, I. C. F. Moraes, C. G. Luciano, Ana Mônica, Bittante and J. A. Sobral Paulo, *Food Hydrocolloid.*, 2011, **25**, 1751.
 20. M. Said Hossam, *Arab J. Nucl. Sci. Appl.*, 2013, **20**, 70.
 21. H. P. Loock and P. D. Wentzell, *Sens. Actuators, (B)*, 2012, **173**, 157.

